

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE BHINNEKA TUNGGAL IKA COCURRICULAR MODULE BASED ON DEEP LEARNING TO IMPROVE STUDENTS' NATIONALISM

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Received : 20 January 2026

Accepted : 25 February 2026

Revised : 01 February 2026

Published : 09 March 2026

Abstract

Globalization will impact the mindset and character of students so that it is required to strengthen nationalism that internalizes the values of Bhinneka Tunggal Ika in co-curricular learning. This study aims to measure the effectiveness of the Bhinneka Tunggal Ika co-curricular module based on deep learning to improve the nationalism of elementary school students. The approach used in this study is a quantitative study with a one-group pretest-posttest design with 25 students as research subjects. The instrument used in this study is a nationalism questionnaire that has been tested for validity and reliability. The data obtained were analyzed descriptively and using the N-gain formula to determine the effectiveness of the use of the Bhinneka Tunggal Ika co-curricular module based on deep learning. The results showed that the average pretest score was 59.36 in the medium category and increased by 21.21 to 80.48 in the posttest and was in the high category. The N-gain calculation showed a value of 0.52 which was in the medium category. This N-gain value indicates that the deep learning-based Bhinneka Tunggal Ika co-curricular module is effective in enhancing students' nationalism. Deep learning can encourage students to understand and internalize the values of Bhinneka Tunggal Ika more deeply and meaningfully. Therefore, the deep learning-based Bhinneka Tunggal Ika co-curricular module can be used as an alternative strategy in strengthening character education in elementary schools, particularly in fostering sustainable student nationalism.

Keywords: *co-curricular module, Bhinneka Tunggal Ika, deep learning, nationalism*

INTRODUCTION

Globalization changes students' mindsets, behavior, and attitudes. In addition, globalization also has an impact on students' openness toward other cultures so that they are able to enrich other cultures, but on the other hand, it may also displace local culture (Tasya et al., 2023). This phenomenon will influence students' nationalism character. Therefore, it is necessary to instill the values of nationalism in students' daily lives to face the challenges in the era of globalization (Girsang et al., 2023). In the current era, the character of nationalism has become an issue that needs to be addressed properly. This is supported by research by Maharani et al. (2023), which states that over time and with the development of the era, students' sense of nationalism has diminished. This issue of nationalism is not something that can be normalized, because the decline of nationalism can be one of the causes of the weakening sense of unity and integrity (Hasrian et al., 2024).

The phenomenon of declining nationalism among students will become a particular challenge in the field of education. This is where the need to instill nationalism from an early age becomes important. Through the instillation of nationalism values from an early age, these values will be embedded and carried into adulthood (Luthfillah & Rachman, 2022). Nationalism is a fundamental attitude that can be developed from an early age and begins at the elementary school level, because at this stage students' values, attitudes, and character are strongly formed. The instillation of nationalism aims not only to prepare the next generation of the nation who have character and a sense of love for their homeland, but also to build awareness of unity in diversity in accordance with the motto Bhinneka Tunggal Ika (Arfadilla & Dewi, 2021). At the elementary school level, schools have an important role in internalizing nationalism values through various learning activities. The internalization of nationalism can be realized, one of which is through cocurricular learning. Cocurricular learning in the Merdeka Curriculum can support the deepening of students' understanding both inside and outside subject matter, which has an impact on character development (Amida & Sulanjari, 2024). The purpose of cocurricular activities is to achieve predetermined learning objectives

that provide authentic experiences (Hueck et al., 2025). This is in line with the opinion of Purnamasari et al. (2025), who state that cocurricular learning is implemented to strengthen, deepen, and/or enrich intracurricular activities in order to develop competencies, especially character strengthening. The nationalism character developed in cocurricular learning is included in the graduate profile dimension of citizenship. Students' nationalism can grow and develop in cocurricular learning when teachers are able to create meaningful learning experiences directly for students. Learning is considered meaningful if the learning activities are meaningful and enrich students' knowledge (Kostiainen & Johanna, 2025). In addition, according to Suyanto (2025), learning is meaningful if the information learned is related to students' knowledge and experiences. Here, the role of the teacher is very important in presenting cocurricular learning so that it provides impactful learning experiences for students. Students will gain learning experiences when teachers are able to understand the characteristics of cocurricular learning itself.

Thus, cocurricular learning activities carried out are in accordance with the objectives of the activities (Rosjanah & Kiptiyah, 2024). By understanding the characteristics of cocurricular activities, teachers are able to design, implement, and guide structured cocurricular activities so that the learning is considered successful. In addition to understanding the characteristics, teachers also need to understand the forms of cocurricular learning activities and their development. Cocurricular activities here can take the form of individual or group activities (Shilviana & Hamami, 2020). This requires teachers to have readiness in managing cocurricular learning. Teacher readiness can be defined as the ability of teachers to prepare learning, implement learning, and conduct formative and summative evaluations effectively (Mataka et al., 2025). Therefore, in cocurricular learning, the role of teachers in preparing cocurricular activities is necessary. The success of learning originates from teacher readiness (Ghalia & Karra, 2023). Good teacher readiness will demonstrate the quality of learning (Qureshi et al., 2025).

In current practice, teacher readiness in cocurricular learning is still not as systematic as intracurricular learning. In line with Lestari et al. (2025), there is a literature gap regarding the implementation of cocurricular learning compared to intracurricular learning. Therefore, this impacts the internalization of nationalism in students, which has not yet been optimal and sustainable. One approach that can be considered effective in addressing this challenge is the deep learning approach. This approach requires comprehensive mastery of concepts and a connection with students' direct experiences (Hariyanti, 2024). In addition, deep learning encourages students not only to fully understand the material but also to utilize the acquired concepts critically and reflectively (Asmi & Wijayanto, 2025). In the context of instilling nationalism, deep learning enables students not only to understand the concept of Bhinneka Tunggal Ika theoretically but also to understand its meaning and application in daily life.

Therefore, it is necessary to integrate deep learning into the cocurricular module on the theme of Bhinneka Tunggal Ika so that it can assist the learning process and effectively improve students' nationalism attitudes. Through the cocurricular module, teachers can use it to build students' character (Yanto et al., 2025), including students' nationalism character. The selection of a cocurricular learning module with the theme of Bhinneka Tunggal Ika encourages students to actively explore the values of Bhinneka Tunggal Ika independently and in groups and to reflect on their behavior and national attitudes. Thus, the learning module is not merely a guide for learning activities but also a learning tool capable of fostering internal and sustainable awareness of nationalism. In accordance with Maulida (2022), learning modules function as the main medium in improving the quality of learning and serve as a reference for systematically structured learning principles.

Studies on students' nationalism have been widely conducted; however, research that specifically examines the effectiveness of the Bhinneka Tunggal Ika cocurricular module using a deep learning approach is still very limited. This gap forms the basis for the need for research that is not only conceptual but also provides empirical evidence regarding the effectiveness of the cocurricular module in increasing students' nationalism. Therefore, this study aims to measure the effectiveness of the Bhinneka Tunggal Ika cocurricular module based on deep learning in improving students' nationalism. The results of this study are expected to provide theoretical contributions to the development of cocurricular learning modules as well as practical contributions for the implementation of cocurricular learning by teachers and schools in improving character, particularly strengthening students' nationalism.

METHOD

The research method used in this study is quantitative research with a one-group pretest-posttest design. The one-group pretest-posttest design is a simple form of experiment that involves only one group, in which measurements are conducted before and after the treatment without a control group as a comparison group (Fahmi et al., 2025). This study was conducted in February 2026 at SD Negeri 3 Kujon, Ceper District, Klaten Regency. The subjects of this study were all fifth- and sixth-grade students of the 2025/2026 academic year in the even semester.

The research sample included all fifth- and sixth-grade students of SD Negeri 3 Kujon, determined through a total sampling technique, namely by involving the entire population as the research sample. The research instrument used in this study was a nationalism questionnaire developed based on predetermined nationalism indicators. The statement items in the nationalism questionnaire had been validated by a material expert to determine the accuracy of the content and tested for reliability to determine the internal consistency of the instrument.

Table 1. Indicators of Nationalism Attitudes

No	Aspect	Indicator
1	Attitudes and behavior	a. Proud to be part of the Indonesian nation. b. Love for the homeland and Indonesian culture. c. Maintain unity and integrity. d. Possess a spirit of patriotism.
2	Knowledge	a. Explain the meaning of Bhinneka Tunggal Ika. b. Explain behaviors that reflect love for the homeland.
3	Skills	a. Create works with the theme of Indonesia. b. Actively participate in the school environment. c. Able to cooperate with peers.

In this study, the classification of students' nationalism scores obtained can be categorized according to the following guidelines (Arikunto, 2016):

Table 2. Categories of Nationalism Attitudes

No	Range (%)	Category
1	81 - 100	Very High
2	61 - 80	High
3	41 - 60	Moderate
4	21 - 40	Low
5	0 - 20	Very Low

Analisis data yang digunakan dalam mengukur keefektifan modul kokurikuler Bhinneka Tunggal Ika berbasis deep learning untuk meningkatkan nasionalisme siswa dilakukan menggunakan analisis perbandingan antara hasil pretest dan posttest diujikan dengan rumus N-gain. Adapun rumus perhitungan N-gain sebagai berikut (Hake, 1999):

$$N - \text{gain score} = \frac{\text{skor posttest} - \text{skor pretest}}{\text{skor ideal} - \text{skor pretest}}$$

The conclusion regarding the comparison between the pretest and posttest results tested using the N-gain formula is based on the following table:

Table 3. N-gain Assessment Criteria (Hake, 1999):

No	Value	Criteria
1	N- gain > 0,7	High
2	0,3 ≤ N- gain ≤ 0,7	Moderate
3	0 < N- gain < 0,3	Low
4	N- gain 0	Failed

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study aims to measure the effectiveness of the Bhinneka Tunggal Ika cocurricular module based on deep learning in improving students' nationalism. The assessment of the module's effectiveness was carried out through two stages of data collection, namely data collection to measure the pretest and data collection to measure the posttest. The pretest was administered in the first data collection before students received cocurricular learning from the teacher using the Bhinneka Tunggal Ika cocurricular module based on deep learning. The implementation of the pretest showed the initial level of students' nationalism attitudes. Meanwhile, the posttest was administered at the end of the second data collection after the cocurricular learning was conducted by the teacher using the Bhinneka Tunggal Ika cocurricular module based on deep learning. The posttest aimed to determine the final level of students' nationalism attitudes after receiving the treatment using the module.

The results of the material expert validation regarding the nationalism questionnaire developed by the author indicated that adjustments to the wording of several questionnaire items were necessary, in order to make it easier for students to understand the statements in the nationalism questionnaire. In addition, the material expert also emphasized the need to conduct pretests and posttests to measure the effectiveness of the developed product. The following are some of the revisions to the wording of the nationalism questionnaire items:

Table 4. Revisions to the Wording of the Nationalism Questionnaire

No	Before Validation	After Validation
1	I am proud to be an Indonesian citizen.	I am proud to be an Indonesian citizen when wearing traditional attire or using the Indonesian/regional language.
2	I like to learn about and preserve regional culture.	I like to learn about and preserve regional culture such as traditional clothing, traditional dances, local foods, regional songs, traditional houses, etc.
3	I participate in ceremonies solemnly	I participate in the morning assembly/ceremony solemnly, calmly, and pay attention to the course of the ceremony until it is finished.

To determine the level of validity of the nationalism questionnaire, the author also conducted a validity test using SPSS version 29 for Windows software. The validity test of the nationalism questionnaire instrument was conducted to determine the feasibility of each statement item in measuring the nationalism variable. This validity testing was carried out by comparing the calculated r-value (r-count) with the r-table value at a 5% significance level. The decision-making criteria were as follows: if $r\text{-count} > r\text{-table}$, then the statement item was declared valid; whereas if $r\text{-count} < r\text{-table}$, then the statement item was declared invalid. The results of the validity test are presented as follows:

Table 4. Results of the Nationalism Questionnaire Validity Test

No	R-Table	R-Count	Validity Result
1	0.2573	0.498	Valid
2	0.2573	0.645	Valid
3	0.2573	0.237	Invalid
4	0.2573	0.042	Invalid
5	0.2573	0.477	Valid
6	0.2573	0.491	Valid
7	0.2573	0.430	Valid
8	0.2573	0.431	Valid
9	0.2573	0.080	Invalid
10	0.2573	0.329	Valid
11	0.2573	0.346	Valid
12	0.2573	0.489	Valid
13	0.2573	0.510	Valid
14	0.2573	0.356	Valid
15	0.2573	0.440	Valid
16	0.2573	0.365	Valid
17	0.2573	0.293	Valid
18	0.2573	0.349	Valid
19	0.2573	0.337	Valid
20	0.2573	0.496	Valid

21	0.2573	0.611	Valid
22	0.2573	0.384	Valid
23	0.2573	0.177	Invalid
24	0.2573	0.687	Valid
25	0.2573	0.534	Valid
26	0.2573	0.480	Valid
27	0.2573	0.334	Valid
28	0.2573	0.217	Invalid
29	0.2573	0.303	Valid
30	0.2573	0.667	Valid

Based on the validity test of the nationalism questionnaire instrument conducted, the results showed that out of 30 statement items tested, 25 items were declared valid and 5 items were declared invalid. Therefore, in this study, the students' nationalism questionnaire instrument can be considered feasible for use in the research after eliminating the five invalid statement items. The use of items declared valid is expected to improve the quality of the instrument so that it is more accurate and precise in measuring the level of students' nationalism. In addition to testing the validity of the nationalism questionnaire instrument, the researcher also tested the reliability level of the nationalism questionnaire using the same software. The results of the reliability test of the nationalism questionnaire are as follows:

Table 5. Results of the Nationalism Questionnaire Reliability Test

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0.810	30

The instrument was tested for reliability using the Cronbach's Alpha technique, resulting in a value of 0.810 with a total of 30 statement items. This value falls within the high reliability category ($0.80 \leq \alpha < 0.90$), indicating that the instrument has strong internal consistency and is capable of providing stable and trustworthy measurement results in assessing students' nationalism levels. After undergoing validity and reliability testing, the nationalism questionnaire was used in the pretest and posttest to measure students' nationalism scores. The overall pretest results of students' nationalism attitudes were categorized as moderate, with details as follows: 3 students in the low category, 12 students in the moderate category, 9 students in the high category, and 1 student in the very high category. Meanwhile, the overall posttest results of students' nationalism were categorized as high, with 13 students in the high category and 12 students in the very high category. Furthermore, to determine the effectiveness of the Bhinneka Tunggal Ika cocurricular module based on deep learning, the results were determined based on the analysis of pretest and posttest data on students' nationalism attitudes calculated using the N-gain formula. The pretest and posttest scores used to calculate the effectiveness of the module are as follows:

Table 6. Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Nationalism Questionnaire

	Pretest	Posttest
Total Score	1484	2012
Number of Subjects	25	25
Average	59.36	80.48

Based on Table 6, it is known that the total score of the students' nationalism questionnaire in the pretest was 1484 with an average of 59.36, while the total score in the posttest was 2012 with an average of 80.48. These data indicate an increase in the average score of 21.12 after the implementation of the Bhinneka Tunggal Ika cocurricular module based on deep learning. Descriptively, the pretest average shows that students' level of nationalism before the treatment was in the moderate category. Meanwhile, after the treatment was given, the average increased to 80.48, which indicates the high category in the posttest. This suggests that the implemented module not only increased students' nationalism scores quantitatively but also improved the level of the nationalism category. Furthermore, to determine the effectiveness of the module, the results of the N-gain calculation can be seen as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} N - \text{gain score} &= \frac{\text{skor postest} - \text{skor pretest}}{\text{skor ideal} - \text{skor pretest}} \\ N - \text{gain score} &= \frac{80.48 - 59.36}{100 - 59.36} \\ N - \text{gain score} &= \frac{21.12}{40.64} \\ N - \text{gain score} &= 0.52 \end{aligned}$$

The N-gain score shows a value of 0.52, which falls within the moderate category ($0.30 \leq g < 0.70$). This proves that the Bhinneka Tunggal Ika cocurricular module based on deep learning has a fairly significant effectiveness in improving students' nationalism. The increase in category, with the initial average of 59.36 (moderate category) rising to 80.48 (high category), indicates a positive change in attitudes after the implementation of the module. These results also reinforce that deep learning contributes positively to strengthening students' nationalism. In addition, these findings highlight the urgency of integrating the deep learning approach into cocurricular activities as one of the strategies for strengthening character education in schools, particularly in fostering nationalism attitudes. Although the N-gain score has not yet reached the high category, this may be influenced by the duration of the module implementation, students' backgrounds, or previous learning habits that tended to emphasize memorization. Therefore, the continuous and structured implementation of the module in cocurricular activities has the potential to further optimize the improvement of students' nationalism.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion, it can be concluded that there is effectiveness of the Bhinneka Tunggal Ika cocurricular module based on deep learning in increasing the nationalism of elementary school students. This is evidenced by the results of the pretest and posttest of the students' nationalism questionnaire, which show a significant increase in scores after the implementation of the module. The pretest results indicate that students' nationalism was in the moderate category with an average score of 59.36. After the treatment by implementing the Bhinneka Tunggal Ika cocurricular module based on deep learning, the posttest average score increased by 21.21 to 80.48 and was categorized as high. This increase shows a positive change in students' nationalism.

Meanwhile, the analysis of the effectiveness of the Bhinneka Tunggal Ika cocurricular module based on deep learning calculated using the N-gain shows a value of 0.52, which means the module's effectiveness is in the moderate category. This value indicates that the module has a fairly significant effectiveness in increasing students' nationalism. Although it has not yet reached the high category, this result also shows that deep learning can encourage students to understand and internalize the values of Bhinneka Tunggal Ika more deeply and meaningfully. This success is inseparable from the principles of deep learning, including being mindful, meaningful, and joyful. Students are aware of their position as lifelong learners (Anggraena et al., 2025), learning is aligned with students' experiences/contextual (Ansori & Heriansyah, 2025), and learning is enjoyable so that it motivates students (Suyanto, 2025). Through cocurricular learning that is systematically designed, students not only understand the concept of nationalism but are also able to implement it in their daily lives. In conclusion, the Bhinneka Tunggal Ika cocurricular module based on deep learning can be used as an alternative strategy in strengthening character education, particularly students' nationalism in elementary schools.

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